

BRAND

Guidelines

BATTERY 2 LIFE

The purpose of this guide is to assist the Consortium in using the Battery2life logo correctly and maintaining the integrity of the project's overall brand identity. It is also a useful aid when instructing typographers and others employed to produce branded items to design and create Battery2life communications material

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Brand Logo

BATTERY2LIFE

The idea behind

The logo of the Battery 2 life project is based on minimal design, clean lines and clarity of the individual elements that make up the mark.

In more detail, we see as the first element the battery icon (in a shape that refers to an electric vehicle battery) and the second element the 2 circular arrows (which have the meaning of circularity, reuse).

These two pure elements come together giving the concept of adaptation but also of interconnected use. They could also refer to the concept / meaning of state of operation (reference to state of operation, reconfiguration, reconfiguration).

The colors that have been chosen are black/white, and 2 tones of green.

A/M clean and minimal color, helps the wide application of the sign (in various sizes), while the two tones of green have on the one hand the meaning of reuse (ecological characteristic)

Dark green and light green can also refer (besides the sense of circularity), in battery indications (percentage by %), reset, ecology and technology at the same time.

Logo Variations

B A T T E R Y 2 L I F E

Positive Format (Primary Format)

Primarily the logo should be used on a white background in its positive format for maximum impact and clarity. In cases where this is not feasible, the versions on page 6 are available for usage.

Logo Variations

a) Negative Format:

This format of the Battery2life logo is only used when placing the logo on an image, a colored background or a pattern.

b) BW/Grayscale Formats

These logo variations are meant to be printed in a grayscale or black and white format (i.e. internal memos).

Color Pallette

Main Colors

CMYK = **C87 M25 Y83 K11**
RGB = **R0 G129 B83**
#008153

CMYK = **C20 M0 Y97 K0**
RGB = **R214 G223 B40**
#d6df28

Additional Colors

CMYK = **C0 M28 Y90 K0**
RGB = **R244 G187 B57**
#F4BB39

CMYK = **C12 M65 Y100 K0**
RGB = **R213 G113 B42**
#D5712A

CMYK = **C8 M38 Y58 K0**
RGB = **R226 G132 B132**
#e28484

MAIN and ADDITIONAL COLORS

CMYK colors are used in printing material.
RGB colors are used on web applications

Additional color pallette can be used for layouts and artworks such as website/posters/leaflets e.t.c. in case you need a small touch of color contrast. These colors cannot replace main color pallette or logotype official colors

Logo Usage

The Clear Space zone around the logo has been determined to ensure the proper visibility of the Battery2life logotype. Maintaining the Clear Space zone between the logo and other graphical elements such as typefaces, images, other logos, etc. ensures that the Battery2life logo always appears unobstructed and distinctly separate from any other visuals. To make sure the logo is always clear and legible, a minimum size requirement was determined. However, when using a lower quality printing technique (i.e. screenprinting), the usage of the logo in a larger size is strongly recommended.

LOGOTYPE PRINT minimum size
28 mm W X 28 mm H

LOGOTYPE SCREEN minimum size
144 px W | 84 px H

Logo Improper use

Display the Battery2life logo only in the formats that are specified in this guide.

The Battery2life logo may not appear in any other colors than the already specified in page 7 of this guide.

Do not rotate, skew, scale, redraw, alter or distort the Battery2life logo in any way.

Do not combine the Battery2life logo with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans or symbols.

Logo usage on social media

Logo use on social media: the logo should be used in a white background.

 twitter icon

 linkedin icon

Logo usage on backgrounds

When placing the logo on an image, color or pattern, it is essential that there is enough contrast between the logo and the background. The logo must not be placed on backgrounds that distract from or compete with the logo.

Typography brand

Must be always used to all communications material and in web and media applications wherever this is possible (i.e. at the Battery2life website), to retain consistency. Replacing the given typeface with others should not be done under any circumstances.

You can download the font family here
<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Manrope?query=Manrope>

Manrope fonts family

Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Light

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Extra Light

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Medium

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Semi Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Extra Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Typography brand

1) For MS templates and publications

HEADING 1

Calibri bold,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2

Calibri bold,
16pt, blue colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3

Calibri bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 4

Calibri bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60 B126)

Body text

Calibri-Regular, 11pt, black colors

2) For Website and other web-applications

HEADING 1

Manrope, ExtraBold,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2

Manrope, Bold,
16pt, black colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3

Manrope, Bold,
14pt, black colors (RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 4

Manrope semibold,
14pt, black colors (RGB R37 G60 B126)

Body text

Manrope Regular, 11pt, black colors

3) For leaflets and other material

HEADING 1

Manrope, ExtraBold,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2

Manrope, Bold,
16pt, black colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3

Manrope, Bold,
14pt, black colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

HEADING 4

Manrope semibold,
14pt, black colors (RGB R37 G60 B126)

Body text

Manrope Regular, 11pt, black colors

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